

UNIVERSITÄT
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CREATING DATA MANAGEMENT PLANS

A GUIDELINE FOR RESEARCHERS AT LEIPZIG UNIVERSITY

Pia Voigt, Leipzig University

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Leipzig, 21.05.2026

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A guideline for researchers at Leipzig University

WHAT IS A DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN?

Data Management Plans (DMP) helps you to structure and organise the management of your research data effectively throughout the duration of a research project and beyond. It sets out how the data generated will be handled to ensure that it remains accessible, interpretable and reusable.

Since generated research data are highly heterogenous as well as the associated collection and processing methods, DMPs should be drawn up on an individual basis. Not all aspects of a DMP are equally relevant to every research project. Depending on your research project, issues such as the data protection regulations may not be relevant. The length of a DMP can range from a few sentences to several pages. It should always be adapted to the current data management requirements of a research project and should therefore be regarded as a living document.

Why Data Management Plans?

A DMP...

... facilitates the reuse and findability of project-related data.

... standardises the handling of research data within project teams throughout the entire data lifecycle.

... helps new members of a project group to orient themselves and understand data management procedures and standards.

... provides clear responsibilities for data management during a research project.

... reduces the risk of data loss and helps to plan and implement the necessary technical measures for effective data handling in advance.

... saves time, as you have already considered all the key aspects of data management before the project begins, including the publication and archiving of your research data.

... enables you to secure funding for your project, as it is usually a requirement for the approval of a grant application.

Guiding questions for creating a Data Management Plan

ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

What is the name of your project?

Who is the responsible project leader (ORCID-ID, contact details)?

Who is responsible for project related RDM (ORCID-ID, contact details)?

Who is funding the project?

Which funding programme is the research project part of?

Which requirements are relevant for RDM in the project (discipline-specific, institutional or funding organisation-specific policies or guidelines)?

DATA SET DESCRIPTION

How would you describe the data collection for your research project?

- Data types
- File formats
- (Expected) volume/size of the dataset(s)
- Data collection methodology
- Potential reproducibility of the dataset(s)
- Versioning throughout the project duration
- Data quality assurance methods (e.g. reproducibility of experiments, data peer review)
- Data organisation (folder structure, file naming conventions)

DATA DOCUMENTATION

How do you document data collection and processing throughout the project?

What subject-specific or project-specific metadata adequately describe your data, ensuring that it is described in a way that is comprehensible, findable, interpretable and reusable by external parties?

If you wish to publish your data in a repository: Does this repository provide a metadata schema?

PRACTICAL ADVICE

Alongside your data collection, create a readme file – [Template Readme-File \(HU Berlin\)](#) – in which you document all relevant aspects that will make it easier to understand and interpret your data. A data dictionary also makes data documentation easier – [Data Dictionary Template \(OSF\)](#).

You can find discipline-specific metadata standards here:

- [Collection of metadata standards](#)
- [Discipline specific consortia of the National Research Data Infrastructure \(NFDI\)](#)

Ask your colleagues or the RDM-team about the standards used in your scientific community.

DATA STORAGE, BACKUP AND ACCESS DURING THE PROJECT PERIOD

What infrastructure do you use to store your research data during the project?

How do you protect your data against loss and damage (backup strategy)?

Who is responsible for storing and backing up the project related research data?

Do you need to implement specific technical and organisational measures to secure your data, such as password protection or encryption?

Do you use high-performance computing to process and store your data? If so, who provides this infrastructure and within what context?

Do several people need to access the research data during the project period? If so, how do you provide access?

Do you need to share data with external project partners? If so, how do you ensure secure and accurate data transfer, for example by using a cloud service?

DATA STORAGE AND LONG-TERM ARCHIVING

What requirements apply to the archiving of your research data beyond the minimum period required by good scientific practice (at least 10 years)?

Where do you archive your research data once your research project has been completed? Can you make use of institutional or discipline-specific infrastructure?

Who is responsible for data archiving?

What criteria do you use when selecting which data to archive?

Which data, if any, can be deleted?

How can you organise the migration of the data, if necessary, to ensure long-term availability?

DATA AVAILABILITY AND PUBLICATION

Is your research data relevant for publication?

Are there any legal restrictions, such as copyright or data protection issues, that would prevent publication?

Who is responsible for publishing the data?

Where would you like to publish your research data? Can you use subject-specific or institutional repositories, or would you prefer a generic option, such as Zenodo?

Is your chosen repository trustworthy? Does it meet the minimum requirements for data protection and security?

Under what conditions would you like to publish your data:

- Open Access (metadata and datasets are freely accessible)
- Restricted Access (metadata is freely accessible; datasets are accessible under certain conditions, e.g. after registration)
- Metadata Only (metadata is freely accessible; datasets are not)?

Which licence will you choose for publishing your research data?

PRACTICAL ADVICE

When publishing your data, you should, where possible, use a subject-specific repository to ensure that your research data is as easily discoverable and reusable as possible for your academic community. If you cannot find a suitable subject-specific repository, please use an institutional or generic repository.

- [Find a repository with re3data](#)
- [Services of the NFDI consortia](#)

LEGAL AND ETHICAL ASPECTS

Who holds the usage rights ([Copyright Act §31 \(in German only\)](#)) to your research data?

Is your data protected by copyright? How can you, if necessary, regulate ownership of the data (contract, licence terms, etc.)?

Is the data personally identifiable ([GDPR, Art. 4](#), [GDPR, Art. 9](#))? What measures must you implement to ensure data protection (pseudonymisation, anonymisation)?

Are there any contractual restrictions that might delay or prevent data publication after the project ends (embargo periods, cooperation agreements)?

Have you, where applicable, obtained approval from your relevant ethics committee (research involving human subjects, dual-use research, animal testing, etc.)?

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES WITHIN RDM

Who is responsible for implementing and complying with the DMP, as well as for updating it regularly?

Who is responsible for the FDM during the project period?

Who is responsible for each of the individual steps in the FDM?

Who monitors compliance with institutional guidelines and/or the guidelines of the research funding bodies?

RDM COSTS

What staff costs are required for implementing RDM within the project?

What costs are required for the hardware and software needed during the project period?

What costs are associated with data archiving, and where applicable, long-term archiving of your research data?

What fees, if any, are charged by repositories for the publication of your data?

Is it possible to apply for funding for the RDM within your project?

PRACTICAL ADVICE

RDM Costs:

- [RDM Funding - Overview of Funders' Data Policies](#)
- [Statements on research data management in funding proposals \(LUH Hannover\)](#)

DMP-TOOLS

- Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) provided by the Saxon state RDM-initiative SaxFDM: [SaxFDM-RDMO](#)
- The consortia of the NFDI provide discipline specific RDMO tools, e.g.:
 - Chemistry: [NFDI4Chem](#)
 - Engineering Science: [NFDI4Ing](#)
 - Cultural Science: [NFDI4Culture](#)
 - Biology, Biodiversity, Ecology: [DMP_gfbio](#)
- DMP-Tool DMPonline: [DMPonline](#)
- Data Stewardship Wizard: [DS-Wizard](#)

CONTACT INFORMATION

You can find all information materials from the RDM-team at Leipzig University at FDM@UniLeipzig on Zenodo and on our website [Research Data at Leipzig University](#).

Do you have any question or need further advice?

Don't hesitate to contact us: forschungsdaten@uni-leipzig.de